

Lukasiewicz 25.02.25

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Sample Name: Proszki

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Image

Live Map 1

ElementOverlay

 C K
 O K

C K_ROI (112)

O K_ROI (44)

kV: 5 Mag: 500 Takeoff: 35 Live Time(s): 1 Amp Time(μs): 50 Resolution:(eV) 138

Sum Spectrum

eZAF Quant Result - Analysis Uncertainty: 6.77 %

Element	Weight %	MDL	Atomic %	Net Int.	Error %
C K	97.8	0.01	98.3	16668.6	5.0
O K	2.2	0.02	1.7	542.8	12.4